

USER-DRIVEN RE-RANKING FOR ADAPTING THE VARIETY IN SEARCH RESULTS

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Abstract

Search systems are a crucial means for users to access information. As only a tiny fraction of the information can be considered in the top search results, this naturally comes with biases that increase even further with personalization, biased databases, or intransparent retrieval systems. We believe that it is essential that users can a) easily understand the characteristics of their search results and b) control them. A prominent example is the presentation of contested political issues, where users may want to understand which view is presented to them most dominantly and change the setting to see more different perspectives. Similarly, when performing a literature search, a user might want to consciously opt for a ranking covering data from different continents or showing research overlaps with other scientific fields. Our work investigates, in the context of literature search, how different demands for variety can be reflected in search results. Therefore, we a) propose re-ranking methods that integrate user-defined variety settings inspired by fairness and diversity metrics and b) present a dataset with variety labels for the broad and multidisciplinary domain of water to test our methods. The experiments show that the proposed approaches effectively adjust rankings to match different variety preferences. With that, we demonstrate the potential of the approach to enhance users' control over search variety, contributing to transparency about entrenched biases and promoting a more user-centered search experience.

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